

Level of Professional Competencies and Identity towards Performance of Beginning Teachers Mediated

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the level of professional competencies and identity towards the performance of beginning teachers mediated by the support system. The main tool used in the study's descriptive methodology to collect data was a questionnaire. The study included contributions from ninety-five (95) Sariaya West District school teachers. For the statistical analysis of the data, percentage and mean were employed. The study found that most beginning teachers have highly competent professional competencies in social, self-management, communication, and leadership skills. Surveyed respondents also have highly observed motivation, commitment, and self-efficacy were observed. The school provides high mentoring and technical assistance support while the support system moderates. Performance is satisfactory in advisory tasks, coaching, teaching strategy, and classroom assessment. Professional competencies and identity levels are not significantly related to the support system and performance. The researcher recommended that school administrators update teachers' profiles with seminars and trainings attended, provide mentoring sessions, and attend workshops on professional competencies and identities. Parallel studies, action research, and quarterly activities can improve teachers' performance. Attending workshops can also enhance professional growth and development.

KEYWORDS: Personal Development, Physical, Social, Technological Devices, Utilization

INTRODUCTION

Teaching was considered a challenging profession, especially for those beginners in the Department of Education. The reality of the teaching-learning process occurred during the real-life experience in the classroom set-up. Teachers also had the chance to do a teaching practicum. However, as Diasti (2021) stated, true teaching occurred after being hired as a teacher. Beginning teachers appeared to struggle with the separation between their personal and professional identities. New teachers perceived it when experiencing the transition from being student teachers to practicing teachers. Additionally, beginning teachers were developing their professional identities. The necessary competencies, knowledge, and skills for professional growth and development were present in teachers, making them more effective.

Understanding teaching begins with building a concept of teaching that goes beyond delving into the mythology of teaching and listing the numerous steps involved. Educators, in particular, became aware of the necessity for research on a particular aspect of teaching to enhance it. Such a process necessitates understanding what needs to be addressed, which can be accomplished more successfully by a detailed review of action records in a classroom setting. According to Berger and Le Van (2018), "identity was strongly tied to the concept of self" (p. 2). Teacher identity essentially refers to how a teacher identifies who they are and celebrates the traits that set them apart from others. Consequently, various factors impacted teachers' identities, including family history, school culture, and experience. A specialist in the field understood the necessity for teaching evaluation but not what teaching was. Since a teacher's conception of teaching informs his behavior, educators must understand what teaching is. The concept of teaching guides all the actions of the learner. In other words, an individual's conception of their function determines the adapted behavioral patterns. Similarly, one's conception of teaching impacts a teacher's performance depending on the suitability of the activities created to carry out specified objectives.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study's main objective was to determine the level of professional competencies and identity regarding the school performance of beginning teachers. The respondents were teachers aged five (5) years and below from Sariaya West District.

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METHODOLOGY

In order to comprehend the dependent and independent variables and to produce a meaningful study outcome, the descriptive-correlational research design was applied.

The correlational design, which examined the relationship between variables without the researcher altering them, was also used in this study (Marzo,2017). It attempted to ascertain the teaching-learning results and classroom supervision in Sariaya West District Public Elementary Schools.

The researcher used an actual sampling technique. The researcher concentrated on 95 beginning classroom teachers across the 23 schools in the Sariaya West District. The table below shows the respondents' profiles, age, sex, educational attainment, teaching experience, and type and level of training attended.

To understand the relationship between the level of professional competencies and professional identity and the performance of beginning teachers as mediated by a support system, a survey questionnaire was divided into five parts: the profile of the respondents, professional competencies, professional identity, mediating support system and performance of beginning teachers.

To ensure the validity of this study, the following steps are taken: 1) define the purpose, specific objectives, target group, and conceptual/theoretical model; 2) locate instruments, evaluate tools already available, and utilize them; and 3) built the instrument and supporting materials. After these steps, the panel members' comments and recommendations should consider the final instrument's structure. The survey covered all the bases to ensure legitimacy, including the phenomenon under study's dimensions. The specialists were also given the questionnaire to examine its organization, content, clarity, and applicability in light of the study's questions. To dependability, the survey underwent preliminary testing in a trial project in one of the unsuitable schools chosen for the study but in a comparable atmosphere to study-participating schools.

The study employed statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Mean. In combining the respondents' evaluations of the school performance, the respondents' professional competencies, professional identity, and mediating support systems are similar. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It employed to know the relationship between level of professional competencies and professional identity as well as the relationship of performance of beginning teachers in Sariaya West District. Mediation Analysis using the Hayes process was utilized to test the instruments by which the performance of beginning teachers (independent variables) affects the performance of beginning teachers (dependent variables) through support systems (mediators).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Summary Table for Level of Professional Competencies of Beginning Teachers

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Self-Management	3.33	0.53	Competent
Social Competencies	3.52	0.55	Highly Competent
Action Research Competencies	3.21	0.54	Competent
Collaboration	3.50	0.53	Highly Competent
Communication Skills	3.43	0.55	Competent
Leadership Skills	3.35	0.53	Competent
Overall	3.39	0.54	Competent

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Competent, 2.50-3.49 Agree/ Competent

1.50-2.49 Disagree/ Less Competent, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree/ Not Competent

Table 9 summarizes the perceived level of professional competencies of beginning teachers. It can be deduced that surveyed respondents in the professional competencies of beginning teachers have the highest mean of 3.52 in social competencies, which is interpreted as Highly Competent. Meanwhile, Action Research Competencies got the lowest overall mean of 3.21; however, still found competent. Overall, having a 3.39 mean concluded the perceived level of professional competencies of beginning teachers, which was competent.

In the level of professional competencies of beginning teachers about social competencies, the respondents were found to promote confidence and effective communication, learning, and thinking. Related Yilmaz & Ilhan (2017) and Adnot et al. (2017) shared that opportunities for student teachers to develop their interpersonal, communication, and teamwork skills were already being given by teacher-training programs, enabling them to use those abilities to support their students' learning more effectively. Additionally, a visualized strategy was described in the interview results as an active method by which teachers can affect their students' performance. The outcome agreed with research conducted by Kucher and Kerren (2015).

Despite that, Action Research Competencies of beginning teachers were in the lowest mean and were still labeled as competent. Khumraksa (2021), Gajdos (2016), and Ula et al. (2017) emphasized that beginning teachers should participate in action research management, which leads to many benefits such as intervention implementation, collaboration with others, and professional development were also observed. Action research competencies should be given focus since this was visible in the daily teaching to

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solve problems or challenges in the classroom and how teachers dealt with the problem-solving scenario.

Summary Table for Professional Identity of Beginning Teachers

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Confidence	3.51	0.52	Highly Observed
Commitment	3.39	0.54	Observed
Motivation	3.50	0.52	Highly Observed
Self-efficacy	3.42	0.52	Observed
Overall	3.49	0.53	Observed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree/ Highly Observed, 2.50-3.49 Agree/ Observed

1.50-2.49 Disagree/ Less Observed, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree/ Not Observed

Table 14 shows a summary of the perceived professional identity of beginning teachers.

It can be deduced that respondents with professional identity in terms of confidence got the highest mean of 3.51 with highly observed verbal interpretation. Meanwhile, professional identity in terms of commitment got the lowest overall mean of 3.39; however, it was still observed. Overall, beginning teachers' professional identity weighted the overall mean of 3.49, which the respondents observed.

In two separate studies, Çetin and Eren (2019, 2022) provide a model for understanding identity by drawing on multiple concepts, including teacher professional goals, teacher identity and teacher possibility and also teachers' achievement goal orientations for teaching, emotions about teaching, teacher identity and teachers' sense of personal responsibility. This implies that beginning teachers' professional identity should have the abovementioned qualities observed in this investigative study.

Summary Table for Support System

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Induction Program	3.45	0.52	High Supported
Mentoring & Technical Assistance	3.50	0.52	Very High Supported
Training and Knowledge Management	3.49	0.57	High Supported
Overall	3.48	0.54	High Supported

Legend: 3.50-4.49 Strongly Agree/ Very High Supported, 2.50-3.49 Agree/ High Supported, 1.50-2.49 Disagree/Supported, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree/ Somewhat Supported

It presents perceptions of the support system regarding the Induction Program. With an overall mean of 3.45, the respondents showed that the support system regarding the induction program was agreed or moderately supported. This indicated that The respondents' perception of the study's support system given to the beginning teachers in the school when it came to mentoring and technical Assistance was highly supported. Indeed, one of the respondents of Podeer & Rahman (2019) stated that "mentorship was crucial for the education sector and ought to be formally included for the teacher educators' professional growth. The National University or the Ministry of Education might formally implement mentorship. On the other hand, a principal who possesses both leadership qualities and mentorship expertise might initiate informal mentoring for the teacher educators' professional growth. Likewise, Hagos et al. (2019) Research has shown that induction programs could effectively assist beginning teachers in forging their professional identities. These programs were designed to provide technicians with a foundation for professional identity negotiation, reflection, and reinterpretation with more experienced teachers through collaborative learning.

Summary Table for Instructional Leadership

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Instructional Performance			
Teaching Strategy	3.47	0.52	Satisfactory
Classroom Assessment	3.47	0.52	Satisfactory
Classroom Management			
Management of Behavior	3.46	0.52	Satisfactory
Advisory Task	3.55	0.46	Very Satisfactory
Extra-Curricular			
Coaching Students	3.53	0.48	Very Satisfactory
Overall			

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Strongly Agree/ Very Satisfactory, 2.50-3.49 Agree/ Satisfactory,

1.50-2.49 Disagree/ Unsatisfactory, 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree/ Needs Improvement

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The results show that the table demonstrates the significant correlation between professional competencies and support systems of beginning teachers. The table shows the relationships between various professional competency levels and systems of support for beginning teachers.

The first column listed different degrees of professional competencies, including self-management, social competencies, action research, collaboration, communication, and leadership. The second column showed various support systems, including induction programs, mentoring, technical assistance training and knowledge management.

The values in the table showed the correlation coefficients between performance aspects, support systems, and professional competencies. The correlation coefficients showed the direction and strength of each pair of variables' links. For instance, a correlation coefficient suggested a significant beneficial relationship between starting teachers' instructional effectiveness and self-management competencies.673** between the two. This link has statistical significance, as indicated by the significance level of 0.01 (2-tailed).

Teachers had a greater impact on student learning than any other factor related to the school system. Because of their criticality to student learning, it was, therefore, imperative that teachers were well-trained and adequately prepared to meet the objectives of their country's education sector (Bettini et al., 2018).The level of Performance of Beginning Teachers in terms of Teaching Strategy is presented in the table.

Test of Significant Relationship between Professional Competencies and Support System

Support System

Level of Pprofessional Competencies	Induction Program	Monitoring& Assistance	Technical	Training& Knowledge Mgt
Self Management	.673***	.638***		.614***
Social Competence	.629***	.611***		.644***
Action Research	.578***	.557***		.532***
Collaboration	.759***	.705***		.679***
Communication	.703***	.676***		.702***
Leadership	.643***	.606***		.533***

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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Test of Significant Relationship Between Professional Competencies and Performance of Beginning Teachers

Level of Pprofessional Competencies	Performance of Beginning Teachers					
	Instructional Performance	Classroom Mangement	Extra-Curricular			
	Teaching Strategy	Classroom Assessment	Mgt of Behavior	of Advisory Task	Coaching students	
Self Management	.603***	.643***	.586***	.590***	.580***	
Social Competence	.576***	.529***	.585***	.566***	.557***	
Action Research	.400***	.467***	.423***	.433***	.497***	
Collaboration	.686***	.632***	.660***	.677***	.656***	
Communication	.705***	.736***	.741***	.711***	.677***	
Leadership	.565***	.606***	.583***	.565***	.617***	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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The outcomes show that a table displaying the test of significant correlations between professional competencies and the performance of beginning teachers illustrates the relationships between various professional competency levels and the performance of beginning teachers.

The first column listed various levels of professional competencies, including self-management, social competencies, action research, collaboration, communication, and leadership. The next columns showed several facets of beginning teachers' performance, including teaching strategy, coaching students, extracurricular activities, classroom administration, advisory tasks, behavior management, and classroom assessment.

The values in the table showed the correlation coefficients between performance aspects and professional competencies. The correlation coefficients showed the direction and strength of each pair of variables' links. For instance, a correlation coefficient suggested a significant beneficial relationship between starting teachers' instructional effectiveness and self-management competencies.673** between the two. This link has statistical significance, as indicated by the significance level of 0.01 (2-tailed). Francisco (2020) conducted a similar study, which stated that a strong relationship exists between increasing teacher capacity and student academic achievement and between teacher classroom management, academic achievement, and teaching style.

Test of Significant Relationship between Professional Identities and Support System

Level of Professional Identity	Support System		
	Induction Program	Monitoring & Technical Assistance	Training & Knowledge Mgt
Confidence	.726***	.764***	.760***
Commitment	.722***	.706***	.717***
Motivation	.719***	.746***	.768***
Self-Efficacy	.760***	.746***	.680***

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This table shows the test of significant links between professional identities and the support systems of beginning teachers. The first column lists different levels of professional identities, including confidence, commitment, motivation, and self-efficacy. The second column represents various support systems, such as induction programs, mentoring and technical assistance, and training and knowledge management.

The correlation coefficients in each table cell, which are key indicators of the strength and direction of the association between performance elements and the support system, reveal crucial insights. Notably, the correlation coefficient has uncovered a significant positive link between starting teachers' confidence and their mentoring and technical assistance, with a coefficient of 764 ** between confidence and mentoring and technical Assistance.

The above results were congruent with the study by Namaziandost et al. (2022), who mentioned that Cognitive Therapy (CT) significantly predicts teachers' professional identity, positively impacting self-expectation, responsibilities, external factors, pedagogy, instructional knowledge, and citizenship behavior. CT levels influence teachers' mental, emotional, and social viewpoints, leading to more accurate interpretation and assessment of their actions. According to Cameron and Grant's (2017) research, beginning career teachers' professional identities could shaped by external, subject-specific mentoring. This led to the conclusion that mentoring significantly influenced these teachers' professional identities. The requirements of teachers and their identities were related.

Test of Significant Relationship between Professional Identities and Performance of Beginning Teachers

Level of Professional Identity	Performance of Beginning Teachers				
	Teaching Strategy	Classroom Assessment	Mgt of Behavior	Classroom Mangement of Advisory Task	Extra-Curricular Coaching students
Confidence	.814***	.770***	.774***	.772***	.721***
Commitment	.710***	.714***	.763***	.688***	.721***
Motivation	.682***	.681***	.662***	.705***	.591***
Self-Efficacy	.680***	.713***	.693***	.645***	.572***

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This table serves as a comprehensive test of significant links between professional identities and the performance of beginning teachers. The first column categorizes different levels of professional identities, including confidence, commitment, motivation, and self-efficacy. The subsequent columns delve into various aspects of beginning teachers' performance, including instructional

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performance, classroom management, and extracurricular activities. This breakdown provides a detailed understanding of the relationship between professional identities and performance.

The correlation coefficients in each table cell indicate the relationship between performance elements and the performance of beginning teachers. For example, a coefficient of .774 ** between confidence and classroom performance suggests a strong positive relationship. Higher confidence levels in starting teachers will likely lead to better instructional performance, a valuable insight for educators and mentors.

Adedigba et al. (2020) showed that classroom management style, as part of management skills, significantly influences pupils' motivation for learning.

This table serves as a comprehensive test of significant links between professional identities and the performance of beginning teachers. The first column categorizes different levels of professional identities, including confidence, commitment,

Test of Significant Relationship between Support System and Performance of Beginning Teachers

Support System	Performance of Beginning Teachers				
	Instructional Performance		Classroom Management		Extra – Curr
	Teaching Strategy	Classroom Assessment	Mgt of Behavior	Advisory Task	Coaching Students
Induction Program	.754**	.762**	.741**	.768**	.758**
Mentoring technical Assistance	.715**	.729**	.700**	.764**	.723**
Training & Knowledge Management	.698**	.714**	.690**	.771**	.724**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation coefficients in each table cell show the direction and strength of the association between the performance component and the support system. An induction program's correlation coefficient of .754**, for instance, indicates a highly positive association between beginning instructors' instructional performance and their participation in the program. Likewise, the correlation coefficient has found a high positive correlation between the induction program and beginning teachers' capacity to manage their classrooms effectively. .762** between the program and classroom management. These correlations were statistically significant, indicating that it is improbable that they happened by accident, according to the significance level of 0.01 (2-tailed).

Sunday-Piaroi (2018) found a strong positive correlation between classroom discipline, pupils' academic achievement, and classroom behavior. This table presents the test results of correlations between the support system and the performance of the beginning teachers. The first column lists the various mentorship and technical support programs, training and knowledge management programs,

Mediation Analysis of Support System to the Relationship between the Professional Competence and the Performance of Beginning Teacher

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	P
			Lower	Upper		
Direct	.2328	.0943	.0456	.4200	2.4694	.0154
Indirect	.5726	.1027	.3538	.7543		
Total	.8054	.0745	.6575	.9533	10.8124	.0000

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	P
			Lower	Upper		
Prof. Comp. --> Support Sys	.8774	.0716	.7352	1.0196	12.2506	.0000
Prof. Comp. --> Performance of BT	.2328	.0943	.0456	.4200	2.4694	.0154
Support Sys. --> Performance of BT	.6526	.0844	.4849	.8203	7.7298	.0000
PC --> SS --> PBT	.5726	.1027	.3538	.7543		

Table 30 shows the mediating analysis of the support system to the relationship between the professional competence and performance of beginning teachers. The results revealed a significant indirect effect of the support system on the professional competence and performance of the beginning teachers. Furthermore, the direct effect of professional competence and performance

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of beginning teachers in the presence of the mediator was also found significant ($p = .0154$, $t = 2.4694$). Hence, the support system partially mediated the relationship between beginning teachers' professional competence and performance.

The statement suggests that the support system provided through mentoring, technical assistance, and teacher training plays a crucial role in mediating the relationship between professional competence and the performance of beginning teachers. Professional competence refers to teachers' knowledge, skills, and abilities, while performance encompasses executing teaching duties and responsibilities. Mentoring, technical assistance, and training serve as a scaffolding mechanism, helping beginning teachers translate their theoretical knowledge and skills into effective classroom practices. By offering guidance, feedback, and opportunities for professional growth, these support systems bridge the gap between theoretical preparation and real-world application, ultimately enhancing the performance of beginning teachers.

Furthermore, by partially mediating the relationship between professional competence and performance, the support system acknowledges the multifaceted nature of teacher development. While professional competence lays the foundation for effective teaching, ongoing support and mentorship provide the necessary scaffolding for beginning teachers to navigate the complexities of the classroom environment successfully. This holistic approach to teacher support facilitates the professional growth of beginning teachers. It improves student outcomes by ensuring educators have the knowledge, skills, and confidence to excel.

The performance competencies and support system show considerable outcomes. In the meantime, the beginning teacher performance showed significant results from the support system, which also showed significant results from the performance competencies. Partially, mediation was noted since relationships can be both direct and indirect.

Mediation Analysis of Support System to the Relationship between the Professional Identity and the Performance of Beginning Teacher

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	P
			Lower	Upper		
Direct	.5004	.1094	.2831	.7176	4.5740	.0000
Indirect	.4094	.1390	.1850	.7259		
Total	.9097	.0589	.7928	1.0266	15.4527	.0000

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	P
			Lower	Upper		
Prof. Identity --> Support Sys	.9649	.0568	.8522	1.0777	16.9880	.0000
Prof. Identity --> Performance of BT	.5004	.1094	.2831	.7176	4.5740	.0000
Support Sys. --> Performance of BT	.4242	.0986	.2284	.6200	4.3028	.0000
PI --> SS --> PBT	.4094	.1390	.1850	.7259		

The statement suggests that the support system provided through mentoring, technical assistance, and training for teachers acts as a partial mediator in the relationship between professional identity and the performance of beginning teachers. Professional identity refers to the sense of belonging and self-concept that teachers develop within their profession, encompassing their beliefs, values, and attitudes toward teaching. Mentoring, technical assistance, and training offers beginning teachers opportunities to strengthen their professional identity by bolstering their confidence, commitment, motivation, and self-efficacy through guidance, feedback, and professional development activities. By nurturing a positive professional identity, these support systems empower beginning teachers to translate their beliefs and aspirations into effective classroom practices, ultimately enhancing their performance.

Moreover, by partially mediating the relationship between professional identity and performance, the support system acknowledges the dynamic interplay between teachers' sense of self and teaching effectiveness. While a strong professional identity provides the foundation for effective teaching, ongoing support and mentorship help beginning teachers actualize their professional aspirations and navigate the challenges of the classroom environment. This integrated approach to teacher support fosters the growth and development of beginning teachers. It improves student outcomes by ensuring educators have the confidence, commitment, motivation, and self-efficacy to excel in their roles and positively impact student learning.

The performance identity and support system show considerable outcomes. In the meantime, the beginning teacher performance showed significant results from the support system, which also showed significant results from the performance competencies. Partially, mediation was noted since relationships can be both direct and indirect. McGeehan (2019) supported the above results, as the research indicated that effective induction programs favorably impact the confidence of newly hired teachers and that confidence has a major bearing on the development of their professional identities. This table shows the mediating analysis of the support system to the relationship between the professional identity and performance of beginning teachers. The results revealed a significant indirect effect of the support system on the professional identity

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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusion:

1. The hypothesis states that the support system and performance of beginning teachers do not support the level of professional competencies.
2. The hypothesis states that the perceived professional identity of the respondents is not supported by the support system and performance of beginning teachers.
3. The hypothesis states that the beginning teachers' perception of the support system is not supported by their performance.
4. The hypothesis states that the support system does not mediate the relationship between the professional competencies and performance of beginning teachers and their professional identities and performance.

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

- 1 School administrations may update teachers' profiles with the seminars and training they attended to ensure a fair distribution of given seminars to beginning teachers.
- 2 Teachers may have a mentoring session and attend seminar workshops about professional competencies and professional identities, which will help them become more upgraded professionals.
- 3 May conduct a parallel study about professional competencies and professional identities through Action Research, and teachers may also apply different instructional performance, classroom management and extra-curricular which will improve their performance in the teaching field.
- 4 Teachers may promote quarterly activities that involve professional competencies and identities that develop their performance as teachers.
- 5 Attend workshop that improve the Professional Growth and Development of the teachers.

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